

THE SCIENTIST WHO FASCINATED EAST AND WEST

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Annotation: This article deals with the cosmogonic views of the great Central Asian thinker Ahmad Ferghani, who, with his rich scientific heritage, made a great contribution to the development of the science of astronomy. In the article, the author also draws attention to issues related to the influence of the scientist's views on the subsequent development of world culture.

Key words: Scientific picture of the Universe, geocentrism, heliocentrism, celestial stars, celestial spheres, celestial equator, equator of the Earth, the meridian of the Earth, the movement of the planets, the eclipse of the Sun and the Moon.

In this regard, we should briefly dwell on the historical role of the Mamun Academy in the development of world science. Until now, many historians have dominated the concept in the development of science of the so-called "European centrism." According to opinion, science and culture arose in Ancient Greece, then "revived" in Europe (Italy) in the 12th and 16th centuries, and Arabic science (that is, scholars who wrote in Arabic) was mainly involved in the translation of Greek science and delivered times of the European renaissance.

This is a completely baseless and even unfounded scientific statement. Because it is known from history that by the 4th century BC Greek science and culture, which flourished in the V-II centuries BC, was in complete crisis. Especially

after the famous Alexandria library (which used to function as a library research center, university) was burned by fanatics of the Christian faith, scientists escaped persecution and fled to cities in modern Syria and Iraq. Here, in Christian monasteries of various minor denominations, work was carried out to translate the works of Greek scholars into Syrian, Jewish and other languages. Therefore, there are some grounds for the ideas of "Eurocentrists" to describe this period, which lasted until the ninth century. But this process alone could not lead to a new upsurge in the history of science towards the "Eastern Renaissance".

The role of the Mamun Academy in the history of mankind is emphasized by some scholars in relations between the West and the East: neither the West nor the East can claim absolute leadership. It was an interaction of both civilizations. As much as Eastern scholars enjoyed Greek science, European science, wandering in the darkness of millennia, "woke up" with the rays of the rising sun of science and enlightenment in the East. The fact that the great German philosopher Hegel, who had a great disdain for the science and culture of the East, uses the phrase "Light from the East" in this regard, clearly demonstrates the worldwide recognition of the scientific potential of the East and is an aphoristic expression of this phenomenon. One of such bright lights is our great compatriot Akhmad Fergani, who introduced the world to our nation, Uzbekistan and Ferghana.

Akhmad Fergani was a great astronomer, mathematician, geographer and engineer. Akhmad Fergani, known as the "Astrologer Ar-Rais", who was awarded the title "Hosib", was called Alfraganus in Europe. Akhmad Fergani made an invaluable contribution to the development of several sciences, including astronomy, astrometry, mathematics, geography, geodesy, hydraulics, geometry and other sciences.

An attempt to characterize the achievements of Akhmad Fergani in science leads to the recollection of his great predecessor, the famous Greek scientist Claudius Ptolemy (died in 168), the author of the "geocentric theory" about the structure of the Universe. It is well known that Ptolemy went down in history with

the famous work “Almagest” (in the Arabic pronunciation of “al-Majisti”), in which he summarized the results of the works of famous Greek and Hellenic astronomers.

According to an article by scientists A. Nosirov and H. Khikmatullaev, “Nilometer” or “Scales of Justice”, two works by Ptolemy (Batlimus) attracted scientists. This is the “Big Chapter”, consisting of thirteen books on astronomy and the second, entitled “Geographical Proceedings,” the next simply called “Geography”. The first of these two works in Arabic is called Al-Majisti [2; 104].

In some cases, the “Permanent Astronomical Table” Al-Majisty was added to it. In addition, Zizi Batlimus, found in Arab sources, is a completely different work than al Majisti. This was known to the Arabs during the time of Harun al-Rashid through the Syrians. According to Academician I. Yu. Krachkovsky, this work was the reason that the Zij terminology was firmly tied to the Arabic language. In the Middle Ages, Ptolemy's Almagest was very popular, widely read and passed from hand to hand. It was unlikely to be an astronomer who did not address the Almagest during the time of Akhmad Fergani. Indeed, this work was the greatest book based on its name (in Latin, the term “Almagest” is translated as the largest).

The most famous translation of the Almagest during the period of Akhmad Fergani was the translation of Hajaj ibn Yusuf ibn Matar (late VIIth and early IXth centuries). Astronomer Sahl Rabbon at-Tabari (first half of the 9th century) made an alternative translation of the Almagest. Another translation of the Almagest was made by Ibrahim ibn al-Salt (ninth century) with commentary. Akhmad Fergani memorized Ptolemy's Almagest and wrote a commentary on him from 30 chapters. This work came to us in eight different titles.

From a scientific point of view, Fergani’s work is not a source of simple commentary. Rather, it combines the ideas of Ptolemy with more advanced scientifically based arguments and new and original scientific ideas. In the third part of the book, Akhmad Fergani scientifically proved that the earth is spherical, this argument has not lost its logic even in the modern world.

“The earth is in the center of the sphere of the universe, and its size in relation to the dome of the sky is as small as the center of the circle, in relation to the circle,”

wrote the great scientist in this work. Akhmad Fergani, who considered any skepticism about things, as the joy of acquired knowledge, he was firmly convinced that the earth is spherical and this truth is absolute for him. From his deep knowledge of astronomy, it is clear that he was able to predict a solar eclipse at a young age when he began his career in Baghdad. The causes of solar and lunar eclipses and methods for their calculation are described in detail in a special section at the end of this work by Akhmad Fergani. Such information is not in the work of Ptolemy.

Akhmad Fergani was not only an astronomer, but also a master of all astronomical instruments. His book *The Complete Book of Fergani* (*Kitab al-Kamil al-Ferghani*) or *The Book of Astrolabes* (*Kitab fi Sa'na al-Asturlob*) describes the theory and practice of astrolabe instruments. "All ideas different from the one we are talking about in the design of astrolabe are inaccurate and efforts are futile," wrote Akhmad Fergani in the book. In general, thanks to the enormous efforts of our great compatriot, astrolabe improved significantly in the ninth century, accuracy increased and was used for centuries as the main tool in astronomical observations. The main role is played by the scientist.

The work of scientists from Central Asia began to expand, through the Silk Road, to the East and West. It is no exaggeration to say that the work of our compatriots Muhammad Musa al-Kharezmi and Akhmad Fergani, who headed "Bayt ul-Hikma", contributed to the development of world science.

The books of Akhmad Fergani were translated into Latin several times in the 12th century in Spain and Italy and were copied in numerous copies and used as a textbook in universities. In particular, his book "Heavenly Motion and the Star Scientific Complex" was twice translated into Latin in the 12th century, and in the 13th century into other European languages. At that time, this book was widely used as one of the main textbooks in European universities. In this work, which is the basis of astronomical knowledge, tracking devices and a sundial are also presented, and its Latin translation, published in Ferrari (Italy) in 1493, is one of the earliest printed books.

In this book, the original title of which is “Kitab fi-character of as-Samaviyya and Javomi ilm an-Nujum”, provides general information about the heavens and stars, the movements of stars and constellations. The Dutch scientist and mathematician Jacob Golius published this book in Amsterdam in 1669 with Arabic and Latin texts and contributed to the spread of the name Alfraganus. Several generations of astronomers have read the works of Akhmad Fergani and become leading scientists. Major European scholars lectured on the activities of Akhmad Fergani. In particular, the famous astronomer and mathematician Regiomontan (1436-1476) gave a lecture on the life and astronomical studies of Akhmad Fergani in 1464 in Padua, Italy. It is especially noteworthy that the works of Akhmad Fergani had a special influence on the work of the famous Italian writer, the great poet of the Renaissance and the poet Dante Aligeri (1265-1321). This famous poet of the Italian Renaissance in his "Divine Comedy" admired the scientific and philosophical views of Akhmad Fergani and placed him among the great geniuses of the world. In his book “The Ball”, the poet cites the results of the research of Akhmad Fergani in the book “Kitob al-Karakat as-samoviy wa javomie ilm an-Nujum” “Heavenly motion and the general book of the science of stars”. More importantly, Dante separately emphasized that the information of Akhmad Fergani is more accurate than the information of other astronomers. For example, the figures given by Dante, in the work “Ball”, that the shortest distance between the Earth and Venus is equal to the radius of the earth times 167, coincides with the calculations of Akhmad Fergani.

The famous scientist and politician A. Saidov in one of his last major publications “Literature and Law” testified: the mention of Dante in the work “Ball”, which, thanks to the generosity of those who activate Venus, it controls our spirit and other qualities, ”is a reflection the teachings of Akhmad Fergani that the movement of planets is connected by giftedness and human activity. Akhmad Fergani’s work says that “the closer the sun is to Mercury, it’s drowning in a wider light, so it’s difficult to see it,” Dante says in the work “Bal” about the same phenomenon: “The second quality of Mercury is that it is immersed in more sunshine than other stars.”

In addition, information on planetary movements and the number of stars in the works of Akhmad Fergani is reflected in the work "Ball". In "Ball": "Until the beautiful Beatrice introduces herself, Venus will have time to appear twice." In the "Book of Movement" by Akhmad Fergani: "Venus makes a circle along its trajectory for 1668 nights or three years and two months." [3; 168-169].

The fact that Dante in the work "New Life" by Aligeri also points to the words of Akhmad Fergani, when it comes to Arab astronomy and counting the year, underlines the great attachment of the great Renaissance poet of the European Renaissance to Fergani's activities. Fergani is even mentioned by Schiller (1759-1805) in his work Wallenstein. In general, it can be argued that in a sense there is good reason to say that Akhmad Fergani is much more popular in the West - in Europe than in the East.

Akhmad Fergani's work on astronomy pays great attention to geography, which describes in detail the climate and location of countries. If we combine the works of a scientist in the field of geodesy, cartography and geography of the Earth, a whole geographical theory will appear. That is why the philosopher I. Yu. Krachkovsky called Akhmad Fergani "a Central Asian astronomer and geographer." Akhmad Fergani is also known as "the first Arab astronomer" who writes his works in Arabic and conducts his experiments in Arab countries.

Akhmad Fergani was the first to pave the way for accurate maps. Christopher Columbus admitted that in 1442, under the direction of the ship "Santa Maria" he traveled on three ships across the oceans and used the maps of Arab sailors to reach the American continent.

In the past, sailing across the Atlantic was a permanent occupation of the Arabs, and the Indian Ocean and the White Sea (Mediterranean Sea), where they dominated for several centuries. It is well known from history that they were experienced sailors. Representatives of all peoples living around the sea served on Arab ships. One Portuguese sailor kept maps created by Arab scholars, and his daughter married Christopher Columbus from Genoa, who then inherited these cards as an inheritance. Columbus tried to organize an expedition based on these cards and kept it a

secret. Scientists from St. Petersburg, in particular, students of Krachkovsky, released this information. When Abu Raikhan Beruni wrote about measuring one degree of the planet's meridian, comparing different points of view and measurements, he evaluated the "Table of the representation of the length of a mile in degrees" compiled by Mervazi and Fergani, like the traditional map of Christopher Columbus, who used his calculations, wrote: "I am fully convinced that Akhmad Fergani's calculations on the degree of the Earth's meridians are correct." [1; 190].

In addition, the Spanish Library of Colombia has a unique letter from a famous traveler, which shows that Columbus relied on the scientific heritage of Akhmad Fergani in his travels and studies. Christopher Columbus went on a journey across the American continent, based on the idea of Akhmad Fergani that the earth is round and spherical. However, he made a mistake in estimating the circumference of the Earth, because he used a unit of Roman measurements of 4856 feet instead of 7091 feet of Arab miles to reduce the distance to Asia.

Akhmad Fergani carefully studied lunar and solar eclipses. During the reign of Caliph Mamun, two observatories were established: one in Baghdad Shammosia; the other is on Mount Kasiyun, near Damascus. The construction of these observatories was completed by order of Mamun under the leadership of Akhmad Fergani closer to reality. We believe that the following considerations will help us arrive at this conclusion. That is, according to Akhmad Fergani, observation from two points will help to obtain a result of greater accuracy in astronomical calculations and at the same time will help to avoid errors in measurements. That is why the observation method developed by Akhmad Fergani led to the construction of two observatories at the same time. In his opinion, this method was used to minimize errors in astronomical measurements. Therefore, these observatories lie on the same parallel and are built with the same geographic width. Akhmad Fergani was the head of the observatories and conducted research.

The study of the solar eclipse of 842 was accurately predicted through hard work, efforts of a scientist and accurate measurements, and scientific observations of this phenomenon were carried out.

Created as a result of astronomical observations in Damascus in Baghdad during the reign of Caliph Mamun, and later known in Europe, which was used for centuries, was called "The Verified Tables of Al-Mamun" ("Az-Zij al-Mamuniy lil-Mumtakhon"). Initially, the creation of this work was directed by Abu Yusuf Yakub bin Ishaq bin As-Sabah al-Kindi (died 873). He was a native of a tribe of Arabs from Basra, at one time he was one of the leading scholars of encyclopaedists, was famous in Western Europe under the name "Philosopher of the Arabs". However, al-Kindi was unable to complete the tables. After his exile during the reign of Caliph Mutawakkil, Akhmad Fergani continued and completed this task.

Akhmad Fergani also enlisted his comrades Khalid Marwarudi, Abu Tayyib al-Yahudi, Akhmad Marwazi and Abbas bin Said Javkhari to complete the unfinished work on the table.

Thus, a group of scientists led by Akhmad Fergani successfully completed the task of Mamun. As a result, the first perfect "Zij" in Arabic science was created, which included 1022 coordinates of stars, planetary movements and other information. He served as a role model for the later Zij and laid the foundation for the science of Zij. The high accuracy and high level of scientific observations of Akhmad Fergani were the scientific and methodological basis for criticizing Ptolemy and measuring the distance between the Earth and other planets that are not found in Greek astronomy.

Another great service of Akhmad Fergani in science is that he put an end to the controversy about the shape of the Earth at that time. He proves that the Earth is round and spherical in such a way that this information has not yet lost its scientific value. For example, the same celestial lights rise at different times, observing eclipses from different places, and so on. In particular, it is believed that various continents and seas (seas and oceans) are located along the entire surface of the Earth's dome. People living in different parts of the world do not see the same

phenomenon at the same time, the rising of the sun and the moon or the setting. As a result, in the east of the sunrise or sunset of the Sun and Moon are not visible to those in the west. If a person travels from the south of the earth to the north, the lights from the north will become better and more consistent. On the contrary, the lights from the south will disappear and become invisible at the end. Akhmad Fergani believes that all these phenomena are related to the fact that the Earth is round and this is proof of that.

At the end of Akhmad Fergani's book on astronomy, there is a table of the geographical coordinates of various places. This table details the boundaries of the prime meridians and climates. It is especially noteworthy that his work mentioned by Abu Raikhan Beruni "The substantiation of the theoretical opinion of Zij" Al-Khorezmi "plays an important role in this. The work has not yet been studied in detail. Undoubtedly, good research and analysis will open new aspects of Akhmad Fergani's work and open up new opportunities for scientists to learn about the popularity of the Middle Ages, and then the East and the West.

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